

Computational scaling of SPH simulations for violent sloshing problems in aircraft fuel tanks

Calderon-Sanchez Javier^{1*}, Martinez-Carrascal Jon¹
and González Leo Miguel¹

^{1*}CEHINAV Model Basin, ETSI Navales, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Avda Memoria n4, Madrid, 28040, Madrid, Spain.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): javier.calderon@upm.es;

Abstract

The wings of large civilian aircraft are designed to withstand a variety of loads whose causes range from atmospheric gusts to turbulence to landing impacts. Aircraft wings are essential structures that demand further research. One of the primary methods used for improving wing design is analysis of the damping effects that sloshing induces on the dynamics of flexible wing-like structures carrying liquids. This will be attained through the development of experimental set-ups that will help in building up numerical models that are used to reproduce the physics involved. Hence, the aim of this work is to analyze the effect of sloshing in reducing the design loads on aircraft structures using the numerical method Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) as the main numerical tool. One of the key considerations in this research is the demand for scaled experiments, making it a necessary step in assessing whether computational tools are able to approximate the registered measurements for different scales accurately. To this end, a numerical model of a vertically oscillating tank built as a fully coupled fluid-structure interaction problem is developed. The structure is modelled through a mass-spring-damper system, and for the inner fluid the δ -SPH methodology is used. In particular, two open questions are studied: the first one is to what extent gravity has an influence on the damping and energy dissipation phenomena when the initial acceleration of the tank is ten times the standard gravity value. The second seeks to confirm that the SPH equations correctly reproduce the scaling laws when the problem parameters are scaled according to the dimensional analysis.

Keywords: SPH, sloshing, gravity, computational scaling

1 Introduction

Challenges in the aerospace industry, and especially those linked to the increase in passenger aircraft size in the near future, demand further research of associated systems that might influence aircraft behaviour during operation. In particular, there is an interest in optimizing the wings of such means of transportation, which are designed to withstand the loads generated from different sources such as atmospheric gusts, turbulence or landing impacts. This goal is hoped to be achieved through the investigation of the damping effect of sloshing on the dynamics of such wings in which the fuel is normally stored, through optimization of their inner configuration and analysis of liquid filling level.

Controlled sloshing has been proved to be effective in dampening movements of analogous structures, and different examples can be found in different industries such as civil engineering, where Tuned Liquid Dampers (TLDs) are designed to mitigate skyscraper's motions when earthquakes occur (Bulian et al, 2009; Tait, 2008) or in the naval industry, where anti roll tanks have been widely employed to mitigate the rolling motion of ships (Souto-Iglesias et al, 2004, 2006). These ideas have recently been studied within the aerospace industry for propellant rocket tanks, as has been noted in Arndt and Dreyer (2008) or in preliminary studies on sloshing on aircraft fuel tanks (Gamboli, 2009).

The main objective of the present work is to extend the knowledge on damping effects due to sloshing on aircraft wing tanks when they undergo initial tank accelerations of the order of $a_0 \approx 10g$, i.e. one order of magnitude larger than gravity on Earth, by analysing the influence of the gravity term in the Navier-Stokes equations.

In a general fluid mechanics context the Froude number represents the ratio between the gravitational forces and the inertial forces. This number appears naturally when the Navier-Stokes equations are expressed in non-dimensional form. In violent sloshing problems, we can usually generalize the definitions of Froude number as being inertial Froude number ($Fr_a = \frac{U}{\sqrt{a_0 H}}$) and gravity Froude number ($Fr_g = \frac{U}{\sqrt{gH}}$) (Tyvand and Miloh, 2012). According to these definitions, U and H represent the characteristic velocity and length of the problem respectively. In this context, H will be considered to be the tank height and U the maximum tank velocity.

When the wing is deformed and accelerated by, for example, an external atmospheric gust, a violent sloshing phenomenon starts inside the fuel tanks. Under these circumstances, Fr_a is much larger than Fr_g , up until the moment when the liquid action is of the order of the liquid weight, i.e. $Fr_a \approx Fr_g$. At that moment, the sloshing dynamics changes, and damping trends show a different regime, as reported by Constantin et al (2020). Since a parametric study of gravity is to be performed in the present work, these changes are expected in the acceleration envelopes of the numerical experiments.

Additionally, we aim to confirm that the scale laws work properly when the geometry is increased in size for the SPH formulation that is used to reproduce

sloshing. Previous SPH approaches of a similar problem have been carried out in [Bouscasse et al \(2014a,b\)](#), where a dynamical system consisting of a periodically oscillating tank filled with different fluids is studied. A non-linear model for motion was used, and the authors focused on the understanding of energy dissipation mechanisms. Similarly, in this work the SPH tool will be complemented by a set of numerical models that reproduce tank motion. The way the tank moves is affected at the same time by the SPH computed sloshing loads. The SPH code used has been previously validated with experimental tests carried out for this problem by [Calderon-Sanchez et al \(2021\)](#). These tests consist of a tank filled partially with water and linked to a structure by a set of springs that allows purely vertical oscillation. The tank is displaced from its equilibrium position, fixed by the action of solenoids. When it is released, the accelerations at different points are recorded. Also the liquid motion is visually recorded with high speed cameras in order to understand the liquid sloshing happening inside the tank.

SPH method has been chosen as the numerical tool to solve this problem. This method has shown reliability previously when used in the context of sloshing problems, where highly fragmented, non linear breaking flow is expected. In SPH, that is a fully Lagrangian method, free surface can be tracked automatically, conversely to alternative Eulerian methods, where free surface definition is a complex matter that might derive into numerical diffusion. Additionally, SPH has demonstrated good capabilities when dealing with impact problems, as it has been reported from several references, such as [Souto-Iglesias et al \(2006\)](#); [Marrone et al \(2011\)](#); [Liu et al \(2018\)](#); [Sun et al \(2019\)](#).

In this work the particular SPH numerical model that has been used to solve the fully coupled fluid-structure interaction problem is presented. In particular, a WC-SPH single phase model is used, where fluid phase is solved by means of the δ -SPH model [Marrone et al \(2011\)](#) and boundary integrals methodology, as implemented by [Calderon-Sanchez et al \(2019\)](#) is used to deal with solid boundaries. The motion is modeled through a forced damped mass spring system and the corresponding differential equation is solved numerically. The emphasis is made on the evaluation of gravity influence and the understanding of the scaling laws.

The paper is structured as follows: first, the outline of the problem is described, second a preliminary perspective of the overall dimensional analysis is presented. Third, the δ -SPH model and the numerical models used for the tank are introduced. Fourth, the results for the two questions previously raised regarding the influence of gravity and the scaling laws are presented. Finally, conclusions are drawn and directions for future work are established.

2 Problem description

As explained in the introduction of the paper, these tanks are placed inside the aircraft wings where the tank movement is mainly caused by the first oscillation mode of the wing. The accelerations corresponding to this mode are dominated

by the vertical direction, approximately $\sim 10g$, which is clearly larger than the other accelerations that the tank could encounter. Consequently, a single degree of freedom model is an accepted approach, and it has lately been very used, as it is reported by [Marrone et al \(2021b,a\)](#); [Martinez-Carrascal and Gonzalez-Gutierrez \(2021\)](#); [Constantin et al \(2020\)](#); [Calderon-Sanchez et al \(2021\)](#).

As a result, the problem can be simplified to a partially filled vertically oscillating tank attached to a spring-damper element. To start the sloshing phenomenon, the springs are deformed and the tank is separated from its equilibrium position and then is released. The tank then oscillates during a few seconds and finally reaches the initial equilibrium position again. For this problem, we define H as the height of the tank, d is the width, L represents the length and h_f is the liquid height or filling level. The corresponding and necessary liquid properties are density ρ and viscosity μ . We denote the surface tension with σ , and θ is the initial contact angle. Figure 1 a) shows a schematic of the experimental setup that can be used as a reference for the problem studied in the numerical context. The corresponding physical quantities are illustrated in 1 b). Regarding the structural components, we note m_s , c and K as the structural mass, stiffness and damping coefficients respectively. If m_l is the liquid mass inside of the tank and m the total mass of the system then $m = m_s + m_l$. The one degree of freedom system is deflected with an initial displacement y_0 and then starts oscillating when the release mechanism is activated.

The evolution of the flow was recorded in the experiments conducted in [Martinez-Carrascal and Gonzalez-Gutierrez \(2021\)](#) and it is displayed in Figure 2. It can be seen that the liquid, initially at rest, is accelerated upwards and the flat free surface starts to deform at a time $t = 0.068$ s. The meniscus travels in the horizontal direction and forms Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities that grow and develop into two jets that impact the upper wall of the tank ($t = 0.09$ s). After the first impact, the free surface is fragmented and a violent and turbulent regime develops with bubble formation and many liquid to liquid and liquid to tank impacts. Finally, for the last low amplitude cycles of the tank motion, the free surface definition is recovered and a standing wave-like regime forms with fewer and less intense liquid impacts.

3 Dimensional analysis

Applying the Buckingham II theorem to the power dissipated by the liquid action, one can establish dimensional relationships between the variation of the sloshing induced damping ratio $\Delta\xi$ and the most relevant non-dimensional numbers, as explained in [Wright et al \(2021\)](#). The damping ratio is calculated following the procedure shown in [Cooper et al \(2017\)](#) as the slope of the logarithm of the tank acceleration envelope. To perform the dimensional analysis,

Fig. 1 a) Scheme of the experimental setup tested in [Martinez-Carrascal and Gonzalez-Gutierrez \(2021\)](#). (1) Load cell, (2) Metallic plate (3) Upper set of springs, (4) Lower set of springs, (5) Laser sensor, (6) Mechanical guide, (7) Accelerometer, (8) Methacrylate tank and C-shaped wooden structure, (9) Pair of solenoids acting as release mechanism. b) Dimensional parameters of the vertical sloshing problem.

we use H , $m_l = \rho H^3$ and $1/\omega = \sqrt{m/K}$ as length, mass and time dimensional units respectively, and we can express the variation of the damping as a function of the following non-dimensional numbers:

$$\Delta\xi = \mathcal{F} \left(Re, f, Fr_g, \frac{L}{H}, \frac{y_0}{H}, r, We, \theta \right) \quad (1)$$

where Re is the Reynolds number, $f = h_f/H$ is the filling level, taking as reference velocity $U = \omega H$ we have that $Fr_g = \sqrt{\frac{\omega^2 H}{g}}$ is the Froude number defined in terms of gravity, L/H is the tank aspect ratio, y_0/H is the non-dimensional initial displacement, $r = m_l/m_s$ is the mass ratio, $We = \frac{\rho \omega^2 H^3}{\sigma}$ is the Weber number and θ the contact angle.

To define a perfect geometrical scaling between the two scales we denote them with the sub-index P (prototype) and M (model) respectively, such that $H_P/H_M = L_P/L_M = y_{0P}/y_{0M} = 1/\lambda$, where $\lambda < 1$ is the scale factor. As an example, when the model is four times smaller than the prototype, the corresponding notation will be 1 : 4, which is equivalent to a scaling factor $\lambda = 1/4$. From this relation, the relevant experimental parameters can be scaled. For the scaling process, we assume that both elongation y_0/H and Froude number Fr_g remain constant. The relevant quantities are related at different scales according to the following expressions:

$$\frac{t_M}{t_P} = \sqrt{\lambda} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\mu_P}{\mu_M} = \lambda^{3/2} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2 Evolution of the vertical sloshing experimental test presented in [Martinez-Carrascal and Gonzalez-Gutierrez \(2021\)](#), at four characteristic time instants, for a water test with a 50% filling level and 10g of maximum acceleration.

$$\frac{m_P}{m_M} = \lambda^3 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{K_P}{K_M} = \lambda^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{c_P}{c_M} = \lambda^{5/2} \quad (6)$$

Additionally, expressions for the relevant scaling laws for the resulting variables – force (F), work (W) and power (\dot{W}) – are respectively given by:

$$\frac{F_M}{F_P} = \lambda^3, \quad \frac{W_M}{W_P} = \lambda^4, \quad \frac{\dot{W}_M}{\dot{W}_P} = \lambda^{5/2} \quad (7)$$

In [Calderon-Sanchez et al \(2021\)](#) a complete non-dimensional analysis of the problem in terms of extra damping added by the fluid has been performed, and the dependency on the most relevant non-dimensional numbers has been

monitored. As viscous dissipation is involved, one of the non-dimensional numbers studied is the Reynolds number. It was observed that only when the Reynolds number is below a critical threshold Re_c , the extra damping barely changes. This critical Reynolds number Re_c is at least two orders of magnitude lower than the turbulent ones considered in our study. As the scales tested are changed in the same order of magnitude, little extra-damping variations are expected due to scale changes. For the water case studied in this paper, very small scales would be required in order to be close to that critical Reynolds number.

4 Numerical model

4.1 SPH model

The Navier-Stokes equations for a weakly-compressible and barotropic fluid can be written in Lagrangian form as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}, & p = f(\rho) \\ \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \cdot \mathbb{V} + \mathbf{g} + \Omega_{ST}, & \frac{D\mathbf{r}}{Dt} = \mathbf{u}, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $\frac{D}{Dt}$ represents the Lagrangian derivative, p is the pressure field, \mathbf{g} is a generic external volumetric force field, Ω_{ST} a surface force field and \mathbb{V} the viscous stress-tensor. The flow velocity, \mathbf{u} , is defined as the material derivative of a fluid particle position, \mathbf{r} .

Based on the weakly-compressible assumption, pressure is determined as a function of density fluctuations through an Equation of State (EOS). In particular, in this work a simple linearised EOS is chosen, such that:

$$p = c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0). \quad (9)$$

Viscous stress-tensor, for a Newtonian fluid, can be rewritten in the form:

$$\mathbb{V} = \lambda \text{tr}(\mathbb{D}) \mathbb{I} + 2\mu \mathbb{D}, \quad (10)$$

where \mathbb{D} is the strain rate tensor, $\mathbb{D} = (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)/2$, \mathbb{I} the Identity tensor and λ and μ the bulk and dynamic viscosity coefficients respectively.

8 *Computational scaling of SPH simulations for violent sloshing*

In this work, the δ -SPH model proposed by [Antuono et al \(2012\)](#) is used. The system of equations in (8) become a discrete set of particles in SPH:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D\rho_i}{Dt} &= -\rho_i \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j + hc_s \delta \sum_j \mathcal{D}_{ij} \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j, \\ \frac{D\mathbf{u}_i}{Dt} &= \mathbf{g} - \frac{1}{\rho_i} \sum_j (p_i + p_j) \nabla W_{ij} V_j + \frac{\mu K}{\rho_i} \sum_j \Pi_{ij} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + \Omega_{ST} \\ \frac{d\mathbf{r}_i}{dt} &= \mathbf{u}_i + \delta \mathbf{u}_i, \quad p = p_0 + c_s^2 (\rho_i - \rho_0) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where j represents a general neighbor particle and V_j accounts for the volume of the neighbor particles j , defined for a fluid particle as $V_j = m_j / \rho_j$. $W_{ij} = W(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i, h)$ is the kernel function at constant smoothing length h . Therefore, $\nabla_i W_{ij}$ represents the derivative of the kernel function with respect to the i -th particle. In the present work, a Wendland C2 kernel with $h/dr = 2$ is used, dr being the particle distance.

Besides, \mathcal{D}_{ij} and Π_{ij} are the diffusive terms added to the continuity equation in the standard δ -SPH model [Antuono et al \(2012\)](#) and the viscous part of the momentum equation respectively. They can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ij} &= 2 \left[(\rho_j - \rho_i) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_{j^*}^L + \langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L \right) \cdot \mathbf{r}_{ji} \right] \frac{\mathbf{r}_{ji}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{ji}^2\|} \\ \Pi_{ij} &= \frac{(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \mathbf{r}_{ji}}{\mathbf{r}_{ji}^2}, \quad \mathbf{r}_{ji} = \mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L$ represents the renormalized density gradient, as defined in [Randles and Libersky \(1996\)](#) and j^* refers only to fluid neighbor particles.

For fully turbulent regimes an alternative formulation derived from the present one, known as δ -LES-SPH, that is based on an LES subgrid model presented by [Di Mascio et al \(2017\)](#) can be adopted for the present problem, see [Marrone et al \(2021b,a\)](#). An analysis of the influence of viscosity for the present problem is carried out in [Calderon-Sanchez et al \(2021\)](#).

Finally, several corrections are performed on the model. Undesirable numerical cavitation occurring in areas where large negative pressure gradients may arise due to inertial forces. This is known in the SPH literature as tensile instability. The accelerations linked to it are considerably greater than $g_0 = 9.81m/s^2$. In order to avoid it, particle shifting ($\delta \mathbf{u}_i$) is applied. In this work, the formulation presented by [Sun et al \(2019\)](#) is followed.

As in this work only one phase is considered, it is necessary to add a free-surface tracking algorithm to the model in order to avoid shifting velocities normal to the free surface. All the details regarding the shifting technique and the free-surface tracking algorithm can be found in [Calderon-Sanchez et al \(2021\)](#).

A general surface tension field Ω_{ST} is added to the momentum equation in Eq. (11) to deal with interface surface forces, which have shown to be relevant for this problem, especially at initial stages when a Rayleigh-Taylor instability is triggered. A similar force term to the one derived by Morris (2000) is implemented here, and it reads:

$$\Omega_{ST} = -\frac{\sigma}{\rho_i} \sum_{\bar{j}} (\mathbf{n}_{\bar{j}} - \mathbf{n}_i) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_{\bar{j}} \mathbf{n}_i \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{n}_k is the normal at the free surface for a general particle k , computed as:

$$\mathbf{n}_i = \frac{\langle \nabla \lambda \rangle_i}{\| \langle \nabla \lambda \rangle_i \|} \quad \text{with} \quad \langle \nabla \lambda \rangle_i = - \sum_{\bar{j}} (\lambda_{\bar{j}} - \lambda_i) \mathbf{L}_i \nabla_i W_{ij} V_{\bar{j}} \quad (14)$$

with λ being the minimum eigenvalue of the renormalization matrix defined by:

$$\mathbf{L}_i := \left[\sum_{\bar{j}} \mathbf{r}_{j\bar{i}} \otimes \nabla_i W_{ij} V_{\bar{j}} \right]^{-1}. \quad (15)$$

For solid boundaries, the numerical boundary integrals approach, as described by Cercos-Pita (2015) is followed. In the boundary integrals formulation, the differential operators from (8) are defined in the presence of a boundary as:

$$\langle \nabla f \rangle_i = \frac{1}{\gamma_i} \left(\sum_{j^*} f_{j^*} \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_{j^*} + \sum_{\bar{j}} f_{\bar{j}} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\bar{j}} W_{ij} s_{\bar{j}} \right), \quad (16)$$

where f_i is a generic field function, \mathbf{n}_j the normal of the surface, pointing outwards, s_j the area of the surface element and γ_i the Shepard renormalization factor, that in this case is computed geometrically through a semi-analytical approach as described in Calderon-Sanchez et al (2019). Note that broadly speaking, in the presence of a boundary, the computation of the renormalized gradient is sub-divided to account for the contribution of the neighbouring fluid particles, j^* , and neighbouring boundary particles, \bar{j} .

Subsequently, in the present work this is the general expression used to compute all the gradients, unless otherwise stated. The approach described in the present work is similar to the one presented recently by Michel et al (2022); Vergnaud et al (2022).

4.2 Tank model

The equation that describes the tank motion can be written as:

$$F_{slosh} - B_0 \operatorname{sgn} \left(\frac{dy}{dt} \right) - B_1 \frac{dy}{dt} - Ky = m_s \frac{d^2 y}{dt^2}, \quad (17)$$

where y is the vertical tank displacement and t the time. m_s is the tank mass, B_0 and B_1 account for the internal damping of the rig, K is the spring stiffness and F_{slosh} the sloshing force.

The equation in (17) is solved using a 4th-order Runge-Kutta algorithm.

The work W_{slosh} done by the sloshing force F_{slosh} , is computed with the following integral:

$$W_{slosh} = \int_{y_0}^0 F_{slosh} dy \quad (18)$$

4.3 Coupling

In order to obtain displacements, velocities and accelerations in the tank, the force that is exerted by fluid motion F_{slosh} is needed. This force is actually the fluid force acting on the tank and being transmitted to the tank. The forces are obtained from the SPH solver according to $F_{slosh} = F_{slosh}^p + F_{slosh}^v$, where:

$$\begin{cases} F_{slosh}^p := \int_{\partial\Omega} -p \mathbf{n} dS, \\ F_{slosh}^v := \int_{\partial\Omega} 2\mu \mathbb{D} \cdot \mathbf{n} dS, \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

with \mathbf{F}_{slosh} being the total force applied on the boundaries $\partial\Omega$ and \mathbf{F}_{slosh}^p , \mathbf{F}_{slosh}^v the corresponding pressure and viscous components.

According to the boundary integrals formulation, these forces can be expressed in the SPH model as:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{slosh}^p &= -\sum_i \sum_{\bar{j}} (p_j + p_i) \mathbf{n}_j W_{ij} V_i S_j, \\ F_{slosh}^v &= \mu \sum_i \sum_{\bar{j}} \left[\Pi_{ij} \mathbf{n}_j + \frac{(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n}_j \otimes \mathbf{n}_j) \mathbf{u}_{ji}}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{n}_j|} \right] W_{ij} V_i S_j. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where the second term of the viscous force F_{slosh}^v is taken into account if no-slip boundary conditions are enforced. A similar procedure to compute the forces is followed by [Chiron et al \(2019\)](#).

4.4 Validation

Figure 3 shows the flow evolution of a δ -SPH simulation of the vertical sloshing problem. The selected snapshots represent the same time instants displayed in Figure 2 and overall there is a very good match of the flow kinematics when compared to the experimental snapshots. The match of the simulation with the experimental snapshots is best at the beginning and end of the simulation when the flow is not fragmented. After the first impact ($t = 0.09$ s), 3D and multiphase effects are involved and the flow kinematics are not captured with

great level of detail. However, the motion of the center of mass of the liquid is well matched by the SPH simulation. The numerical simulations obtained with our code have been previously validated with experiments and these comparisons have been reported in previous papers such as [Marrone et al \(2021a\)](#) and [Calderon-Sanchez et al \(2021\)](#). In those articles the numerical convergence of the method is studied and a complete validation against experimental measurements is performed for different fluids (water, acetone, oil and glycerine) in terms of sloshing force, tank kinematics and energy dissipation. An example of this validation procedure will be shown in [Figures 6 and 7](#) in terms of tank acceleration and decay envelope where we see a reasonable match between the SPH simulation and experimental data.

Fig. 3 Flow evolution of a water, 50% filling level and 10g maximum acceleration FSI δ -SPH simulation of the vertical sloshing problem. The snapshots represent the simulated counterparts of the experimental snapshots presented in [Figure 2](#).

5 Results

In this section, the results for two numerical campaigns are presented. First, the effect of gravity on the overall damping is assessed. Then, simulations are carried out at different scales following the dimensional analysis presented in [section 4](#). Even though filling height h_f , represented in the analysis through non-dimensional number f can be varied, in this work it is kept constant and therefore all results presented refer to a filling level $f = 0.5$.

Compact support and speed of sound are chosen the same for both the gravity and the scale studies, such that $h/dr = 2$ and $c_s = 30$ m/s. Resolution is established in terms of the vertical number of particles as $h_f/dr = 100$. Initially, a meniscus is added to the liquid free surface near the wall. The influence of the meniscus in this problem has already been assessed by [Calderon-Sanchez et al \(2021\)](#). For this work, the meniscus length is set at $l = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m and $\theta = 45^\circ$. All the tests carried out in this work assume that the fluid tested is water at standard conditions. Then, $\rho = 998$ kg/m³, $\mu = 8.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$ Pa \cdot s and $\sigma = 0.072$ N/m.

The tank is displaced initially to a position $y = y_0$. Then, when the release is activated it is allowed to oscillate freely, measuring the overall force, position, velocity and acceleration. In all cases studied, the initial displacement is always the same, corresponding to $y_0 = H$.

In order to establish a comparison reference, a preliminary test without liquid is carried out. The liquid mass is replaced by structural mass with a

total weight corresponding to a 50% filling condition. This results in the same total nominal mass for all the tests presented in this study.

5.1 Gravity study

The present section is devoted to test how important gravity's action is in this FSI problem. Consequently, three different values of the gravity value $g = 0.1g_0$, g_0 and $5g_0$, with $g_0 = 9.8 \text{ m/s}^2$ will be used and the results will be compared. For each of the gravity values, three different facilities characterized by their respective damping parameters, see Table 1, will be tested. As the mass and the spring constants are not changed, the characteristic frequency of the problem remains constant for all the combinations of gravity values and damping parameters. These three facilities are: the experimental rig constructed in the UPM facilities, [Martinez-Carrascal and Gonzalez-Gutierrez \(2021\)](#), and an under-damped and over-damped version of the same experimental facilities.

The variation of the structural damping in this gravity study is performed in order to test how dependant gravity's role is on the structural damping of the rig.

Table 1 Structural damping coefficients for the three studied facilities.

	$B_0 [N]$	$B_1 [kg/s]$
Under-damped	0	1
UPM	0.38	1.73
Over-damped	0.8	2.5

The tank acceleration obtained when the UPM, under-damped and over-damped systems are tested are presented as a function of time in Figures 4, 6 and 9, and as the logarithm of the acceleration envelope in Figures 5, 7 and 10. The first idea that can be extracted is that for the reference value $g = g_0$ and the under-gravity case $g = g_0/10$ the results are very similar for the three different facilities, showing that the absence of gravity and the reference gravity have little influence on the tank acceleration damping. Of course, if the gravity value is increased to $5g_0 = a_0/2$, then its influence is clearly relevant, changing the behavior of the decaying curve considerably. This happens because when the gravity is increased the relative motion of the liquid with respect to the motion of the tank is attenuated sooner, and the liquid recovers a block-like behaviour, acting as an added mass so the trend is similar to the dry experiment, i.e. the liquid behaves as a solid mass. This observation is demonstrated by looking at the flow kinematics displayed in Figure 8. It is seen that for the $g = 0$ case the liquid is allowed to freely slosh with high fragmentation of the free surface and many liquid impacts whereas for the $g = 5g_0$ case, the liquid is not even able to produce the first liquid

impact against the upper wall of the tank and it displays very little relative motion with respect to the tank.

Fig. 4 Evolution of the tank acceleration with different gravity values for the case with damping parameters: $B_0 = 0$ N and $B_1 = 1$ kg/s.

Fig. 5 Logarithm of the acceleration envelope with different gravity values for the case with damping parameters: $B_0 = 0$ N and $B_1 = 1$ kg/s.

Another important idea that can be extracted from these results is that the role of gravity is quite independent of the mechanical damping of the particular rig used. This can be concluded as we have shown that all the structural damping values used have a very similar effect in terms of gravity's influence.

Fig. 6 Evolution of the tank acceleration with different gravity values for the case with damping parameters: $B_0 = 0.38$ N and $B_1 = 1.73$ kg/s. Experimental data obtained in [Martinez-Carrascal and Gonzalez-Gutierrez \(2021\)](#) has been plotted as comparison.

Fig. 7 Logarithm of the acceleration envelope with different gravity values for the case with damping parameters: $B_0 = 0.38$ N and $B_1 = 1.73$ kg/s. Experimental data obtained in [Martinez-Carrascal and Gonzalez-Gutierrez \(2021\)](#) has been plotted as comparison.

5.2 SPH scaling

Initial results from experimental UPM facilities were carried out at scale 1:5. In this work, this scale is reproduced, and two other scales, namely 2:5 and 3:5 are used in order to analyse them numerically. Results are all scaled up to the wing size applying the scaling laws.

In Figure 11 the acceleration curves corresponding to each of the three different scales is presented. As can be observed, the scaling laws work perfectly and the acceleration curves of the three scales are very similar. The equivalent logarithm of the acceleration envelope is also represented for the three scales in Figure 12, showing a similar trend.

Fig. 8 Comparison of the flow evolution of δ -SPH simulations for cases with $g = 0$ and $g = 5g_0$ in the UPM facility.

Fig. 9 Evolution of the tank acceleration with different gravity values for the case with damping parameters: $B_0 = 0.8$ N and $B_1 = 2.5$ kg/s.

Fig. 10 Logarithm of the acceleration envelope with different gravity values for the case with damping parameters: $B_0 = 0.8$ N and $B_1 = 2.5$ kg/s.

Fig. 11 Evolution of the tank acceleration for the three different scales.

Fig. 12 Logarithm of the acceleration envelope for the three different scales.

Additionally, the forces for the three scales are compared in Figure 13. We can observe that very similar values are obtained for all scales, meaning that the scaling laws reproduce the expected force values. Some discrepancies can be observed at peak values for the three different scales, especially at first stages. This is particularly noticeable for the larger scale. As it is illustrated in Figures 3 and 8, first cycles are characterized by very thin jets that impact the wall. When this happens, excessively high pressures might be obtained at certain locations where the number of neighbors is low, having an impact on the forces that are computed. This trend reduces as the simulation evolves.

In Figure 14, the work performed by the sloshing force is computed according to equation (18), where the force plays a role, at the three different scales. As such, the discrepancies can be traced to the discussion on the sloshing force results presented above. Noting that the work is an integral quantity, the effect is greater at later stages, where curves follow the same trend, but with

Fig. 13 Full Scaled sloshing force obtained with the extrapolation from the three scales.

an offset. For comparison, the results for each scale are divided by λ^4 as it is indicated by the second equation of (7).

Fig. 14 Full scale Work produced by the sloshing force obtained with the extrapolation from the three scales.

We should remark on the clear advantages of making a scaling study based on computation fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations. In this approach all the fluid parameters can be forced in order to keep all the non-dimensional numbers equal at the different scales. In contrast to the CFD study, in the experimental approach to this coupled fluid-structure problem, the possibility of forcing all the dominant non-dimensional numbers to be equal at different scales is not possible, and consequently larger uncertainties appear when the scales change.

6 Conclusions

In this work, a numerical model of a fully coupled fluid-structure interaction problem is developed. The aim is to analyze the influence of gravity and the scale changes on the damping effects due to liquid sloshing inside the fuel tanks of aircraft wings.

The influence of gravity is very low in this kind of problem with initial acceleration an order of magnitude higher than the typical reference value $g_0 = 9.8m/s^2$. More intense values of gravity are required to have a relevant impact on the acceleration damping. The variation of the damping parameters gives us the confirmation that the gravity's role behaves the same for all cases, allowing this conclusion to be highly generalizable.

Scaling process is necessary to predict wing loading at full scale. Experiments might be limited at some point of the process, as the variation of non-dimensional numbers depend on the existing fluid characteristics. This also implies that normally non-dimensional relations cannot be changed on its own, influencing others. These aspects make numerical analysis an important tool to perform the extrapolation process, as it allows greater flexibility and a larger range of variation for non-dimensional relations.

This paper has investigated the scaling properties of the proposed system by means of the δ -SPH model for the fluid, and a mass-spring-damper system for the tank motion. The results show that the numerical model presented is able to predict the sloshing forces, the tank accelerations and the work produced by the sloshing force in the full scale experiment successfully from the results obtained at different scales. Therefore, from this work it can be concluded that having validated results at one scale is enough to obtain results at any scale, just by applying the corresponding scaling laws. This is a crucial aspect from the perspective of computational time savings.

Acknowledgments

This research is receiving funding from European Union (EU) under H2020 grant 815044 “*Sloshing Wing Dynamics (SLOWD)*” .

The authors also acknowledge the financial support from the Spanish Ministry for Science, Innovation and Universities (MCIU) under grant RTI2018-096791-B-C21 “*Hidrodinámica de elementos de amortiguamiento del movimiento de aerogeneradores flotantes*”.

This research has also received funding from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid under a pre-doctoral scholarship.

References

- Antuono M, Colagrossi A, Marrone S (2012) Numerical diffusive terms in weakly-compressible SPH schemes. *Computer Physics Communications* 183(12):2570–2580

- Arndt TO, Dreyer ME (2008) Damping behavior of sloshing liquid in laterally excited cylindrical propellant vessels. *Journal of Spacecraft and rockets* 45(5):1085–1088
- Bouscasse B, Colagrossi A, Souto-Iglesias A, et al (2014a) Mechanical energy dissipation induced by sloshing and wave breaking in a fully coupled angular motion system. I. theoretical formulation and numerical investigation. *Physics of Fluids* 26(3):033,103
- Bouscasse B, Colagrossi A, Souto-Iglesias A, et al (2014b) Mechanical energy dissipation induced by sloshing and wave breaking in a fully coupled angular motion system. II. experimental investigation. *Physics of Fluids* 26(3):033,104
- Bulian G, Souto-Iglesias A, Delorme L, et al (2009) Smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) simulation of a tuned liquid damper (TLD) with angular motion. *Journal of Hydraulic Research* 47(extra issue):28–39
- Calderon-Sanchez J, Cercos-Pita J, Duque D (2019) A geometric formulation of the shepard renormalization factor. *Computers & Fluids* 183:16 – 27. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compfluid.2019.02.020>
- Calderon-Sanchez J, Martinez-Carrascal J, Gonzalez-Gutierrez L, et al (2021) A global analysis of a coupled violent vertical sloshing problem using an SPH methodology. *Engineering Applications of Computational Fluid Mechanics* 15(1):865–888
- Cercos-Pita JL (2015) Aquagpusph, a new free 3D SPH solver accelerated with OpenCL. *Computer Physics Communications* 192:295–312
- Chiron L, De Lefle M, Oger G, et al (2019) Fast and accurate SPH modelling of 3-D complex wall boundaries in viscous and non viscous flows. *Computer Physics Communications* 234:93–111
- Constantin L, Courcy JD, Titurus B, et al (2020) Analysis of damping from vertical sloshing in a SDOF system. *Mechanical Systems Signal Processing*
- Cooper JE, Emmet PR, R. WJ (2017) Envelope function - a tool for analyzing flutter data. *International Forum on Aeroelasticity and Structural Dynamics*
- Di Mascio A, Antuono M, Colagrossi A, et al (2017) Smoothed particle hydrodynamics method from a large eddy simulation perspective. *Physics of Fluids* 29(3):035,102
- Gamboli F (2009) Fuels loads in large civil airplanes. In: 4th ERCOFTAC SPHERIC workshop on SPH applications

- Liu W, Sun P, Ming F, et al (2018) Application of particle splitting method for both hydrostatic and hydrodynamic cases in SPH. *Acta Mechanica Sinica* 34(4):601–613
- Marrone S, Colagrossi A, Antuono M, et al (2011) A 2D+t SPH model to study the breaking wave pattern generated by fast ships. *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 27(8):1199–1215
- Marrone S, Colagrossi A, Calderon-Sanchez J, et al (2021a) Numerical study on the dissipation mechanisms in sloshing flows induced by violent and high-frequency accelerations. ii. comparison against experimental data. *Physical Review Fluids* 6(11):114,802
- Marrone S, Colagrossi A, Gambioli F, et al (2021b) Numerical study on the dissipation mechanisms in sloshing flows induced by violent and high-frequency accelerations. i. theoretical formulation and numerical investigation. *Physical Review Fluids* 6(11):114,801
- Martinez-Carrascal J, Gonzalez-Gutierrez L (2021) Experimental study of the liquid damping effects on a SDOF vertical sloshing tank. *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 100:103,172
- Michel J, Vergnaud A, Oger G, et al (2022) On particle shifting techniques (PSTs): Analysis of existing laws and proposition of a convergent and multi-invariant law. *Journal of Computational Physics* 459:110,999
- Morris JP (2000) Simulating surface tension with smoothed particle hydrodynamics. *International journal for numerical methods in fluids* 33(3):333–353
- Randles P, Libersky L (1996) Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics: some recent improvements and applications. *Computer methods in applied mechanics and engineering* 39:375–408
- Souto-Iglesias A, Rojas LP, Rodríguez RZ (2004) Simulation of anti-roll tanks and sloshing type problems with smoothed particle hydrodynamics. *Ocean Engineering* 31:1169–1192
- Souto-Iglesias A, Delorme L, Pérez-Rojas L, et al (2006) Liquid moment amplitude assessment in sloshing type problems with smooth particle hydrodynamics. *Ocean Engineering* 33:1462–1484
- Sun P, Colagrossi A, Marrone S, et al (2019) A consistent approach to particle shifting in the δ -plus-SPH model. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 348:912–934
- Tait M (2008) Modelling and preliminary design of a structure-TLD system. *Engineering Structures* 30(10):2644–2655

- Tyvand PA, Miloh T (2012) Incompressible impulsive sloshing. *Journal of fluid mechanics* 708:279–302
- Vergnaud A, Oger G, Le Touzé D, et al (2022) C-CSF: Accurate, robust and efficient surface tension and contact angle models for single-phase flows using sph. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 389:114,292
- Wright M, Gambioli F, Malan A (2021) A non-dimensional characterization of structural vibration induced vertical slosh induced damping. The 31st International Ocean and Polar Engineering Conference ISOPE-I-21-3211